

اسلام اور غير الہامی مذاہب میں خواتین کے حقوق کا تقابلی و تنقیدی جائزہ

A Comparative and Critical Analysis of Women's Rights in Islam and non-Theistic Religions

Sibghat Ullah

PhD Research Scholar in Islamic Studies, Metropolitan University, Karachi

Dr. Mubashira

Ph. D Research Scholar, Department of Islamic Studies, Federal Urdu University, Abdul Haq Campus, Karachi

Abdullah Kareem

Department of Islamic Studies, Metropolitan, University, Karachi

Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies
01-13

© The Author (s) 2026

Volume:6, Issue:1, 2026

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

OJS **PKP**
OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEMS PUBLIC KNOWLEDGE PROJECT

Abstract

When the Almighty Allah created humans, He sent prophets from among humans for their religious and moral education so that they could educate humans in all aspects of religion and worldly life through the message brought by the Almighty, and humans could recognize their position that the Almighty gave them. With the passing of time, where humans believed in the Almighty in the confirmations of the prophets, humans openly acknowledged the great and superior God and disobeyed, as a result of which, on the one hand, those people came into existence who followed the law brought by the prophets from God, those people were called Semitic, that is, followers of Semitic or uninspired religions, and on the other hand, those people came to the fore who, while denying the law of the prophets, set up their own religious and worldly, social and cultural, economic and military laws in contrast to their teachings. The basis of which was extremely market-oriented reason. The enforcers of these self-imposed laws are called followers of non-Semitic (non-inspired) religions. These include Hinduism, Buddhism, Sikhism and Jainism in particular. These are religions in which each of them has talked about the rights of women, but women are not at all satisfied with their rights. In comparison, women in Islam are fortunate in every way. The article under review has analyzed and compared the nature of women's rights in these non-Semitic or non-inspired religions and whether women are comfortable with their rights or are skeptical. This analysis will show that the religion that firmly protects women's rights in every respect is the best.

Keywords: Women's Rights, Islam, Non-Theistic Religions, Comparative Religious Studies.

Corresponding Author Email:

sibghat12@gmail.com

mubashirahmuzzafferlatif@gmail.com

abkareem789@gmail.com